

A Study on the Effect of pH Values on Magneto-Optic Properties of Fe₃O₄ Nanoferrofluids

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Abstract

Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles have been synthesized at different pH values of co-precipitator (NaOH) using co-precipitation method with oleic acid as surfactant. Structural characterization was done using X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique and the crystallite sizes of the samples were calculated by Scherrer approximation from the full width half maximum value of (311) plane. The particle sizes are in the range of 6.48nm, 7.18nm and 7.66nm. Surface morphology and the chemical composition of the samples were investigated using Scanning electron microscope (SEM) with EDAX analysis. Magnetic parameters of the sample such as Saturation magnetization (M_s), Remanence (M_r) and Coercivity (H_c) were measured using vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) at room temperature. Verdet constant of the samples were calculated from Faraday rotation for various magnetic fields and it varies from 5.02×10^{-4} deg./G cm to 8.04×10^{-4} deg./G cm.

Keywords: Co-precipitation, Saturation Magnetization, Remanence, Coercivity, Faraday rotation, Verdet constant.